

PECULIARITIES OF THE COURSE IN PATIENTS WITH PRIMARY OPEN ANGLE GLAUCOMA WITH HYPERTENSION

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Annotation: Glaucoma is a group of diseases differing in pathophysiology, risk factors, manifestations, treatment and prognosis. Progressive degeneration of the optic nerve with the loss of retinal ganglion cells, thinning of the retinal nerve fiber layer and progressive optic disc excavation are their common feature.

Keywords: glaucoma, optic disc excavation, intraocular pressure

Introduction. Primary open angle glaucoma is currently characterized by a pattern of progressive retinal ganglion cell loss due to a complex underlying pathophysiology that remains poorly elucidated. The role of blood flow and intraocular pressure (IOP) in the pathogenesis of glaucoma has been widely studied. In addition, it has been established that lowering IOP can slow the progression of glaucoma. In addition, a number of influencing factors have emerged and gained strength over the years. Increasing evidence points to the contribution of low cerebrospinal fluid pressure, autoimmunity, neurodegeneration and autoregulation disorders to the pathophysiology of glaucoma.

Purpose of the study: To investigate the main indices of systemic and cerebral hemodynamics in POAG patients with different BP levels.

Materials and Methods. 90 patients with primary open angle glaucoma combined with hypertension were examined. Systemic hemodynamics of the patients with estimation of coefficient of variability of systolic and diastolic blood pressure as well as cerebral hemodynamics with estimation of vasomotor reactivity during stress test and parameters of ocular hemodynamics in POAG patients with various levels of BP in the dynamics of the disease have been studied.

Results: We studied 91 eyes of patients with primary open angle glaucoma combined with hypertension, 41 men (40%) and 50 women (60%). The control group consisted of 27 eyes of healthy subjects of similar age who had no ophthalmopathy. The mean age was 61.49 ± 9.58 years (33.5-87.9). The mean age of men was 60.1 ± 8.7 years and of women 62.11 ± 10.1 years. Among those who fell ill, 26.4% (n=24) had no medical history. IOP of most patients was within normal limits, i.e., <20 mmHg.

Conclusions: IOP remains a major risk factor for glaucoma evaluation and progression; No significant difference was found in central corneal thickness (CCT) and endothelial cell density (endothelial cells) of glaucoma compared to corneas of healthy patients. IOP patients have relatively thinner corneas, while POAG patients have thicker corneas. Thus, IOP should be adjusted based on corneal thickness to avoid over- or underestimating.

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